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A 68-year-old woman presented asymptomatic purplish-colored alterations on both the ventral surface of the tongue and the sublingual caruncles. After the clinical examination, it is determined that the alterations correspond to sublingual varicosities. Varicosities are abnormally dilated veins, which are commonly seen in the elderly. They may be seen in any location, but often involve the lips, buccal and labial mucosa and ventral tongue. Its etiology is unknown, but may be associated with weakening of the vessel wall consequent to aging. No treatment is necessary except for esthetic reasons. The sublingual varicosidades have a good prognosis, although occasional lesions may become thrombosed. Varicosities at lips may sometimes resemble mucocoeles.

Sublingual varicosities

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